

Uncovering Mental Health Stigma with Digital Information-Seeking Behavioral Patterns in Mexico

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Introduction:

According to the British Journal of Psychiatry, around 16% of people in Mexico suffer from mental disorders like anxiety, depression, and substance abuse. Previous studies investigated factors that elevate the prevalence of mental illness like treatment barriers, and poverty. However, there is little research exploring how mental health stigma influences digital information-seeking behaviors on these mental illnesses. Determining patterns in online searches could inform future efforts to reduce stigma and improve treatment accessibility.

Objectives:

We aim to determine the patterns that emerge in digital mental health information-seeking behaviors (DMHISB) in Mexico in order to reduce mental health stigma and improve access to mental health care.

Methods:

We entered these search terms into Google Trends: *stigma/estigma*, *depression/depresión*, *anxiety/ansiedad*, and *substance abuse/abuso de sustancias*. We conducted an intra-language analysis examining patterns in Mexico from 1/01/15 to 1/01/25. We performed an inter-language analysis individually comparing each term's web search popularity while keeping all other variables constant.

Results:

The intra-language analysis revealed that the highest average relative search interest (ARSI) was “Depression” (English) (M = 64, SD = 10) which reached peak popularity in July 2024, and “ansiedad” (Spanish) at (M = 54, SD = 25) peaking in August 2022. Comparing all terms in the inter-language analysis, the ARSI’s and SD’s are as follows: ‘Depresión’ (M = 28, SD = 18), ‘depression’ (M = 5, SD = 1), ‘estigma’ (M = 42, SD = 11), ‘stigma’ (M = 16, SD = 6), ‘ansiedad’ (M = 54, SD = 25), ‘anxiety’ (M = 2, SD = 1), ‘abuso de sustancias’ (M = 42, SD = 22), and ‘substance abuse’ (M = 7, SD = 8). Standard errors ranged from ±0.06 (anxiety) to ±2.24 (ansiedad). Spanish terms “abuso de sustancias” (M = 42.0) and estigma (M = 42.2) had similarly high ARSI values.

Discussion:

During 1/15/15 - 1/01/25, search popularity for ‘anxiety’ and ‘ansiedad’ rose near the end relative to other terms. Recent popularity may reflect high interest in anxiety as a mental health issue, implying a possible need to improve treatment access and reduce harmful societal views on mental illness. High search interest in ‘ansiedad’, ‘abuso de sustancias’, and ‘estigma’ may reflect a concern towards scrutiny and tendencies to engage in DMHISB to self-diagnose or gain awareness. Finally, since ‘ansiedad’ had the lowest variability of Spanish terms there is stable interest in this condition.

References:

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